

Modular Framework for Federated HPC-Cloud and Quantum Workflows

Tomislav Šubić¹, Evangelos Raptis², Ioannis Liliopoulos^{3,4}, Georgios D. Varsamis^{3,4}, Konstantinos Rallis^{3,4}, Evangelos Tsipas^{3,4}, Panagiotis Dimitrakis³, Georgios Ch. Sirakoulis⁴, Marco Mamei⁵, Daniele Toti⁶, Natalia Selini Hadjidimitriou^{*6}

¹ ARCTUR d.o.o., Industrijska cesta 1a, 5000 Nova Gorica, Slovenia

² AEGIS IT Research GmbH, Humboldtstraße 25, 38106 Braunschweig, Germany

³ NCSR "Demokritos", Patr. Gregoriou E' & 27 Neapoleos Str., 153 41 Agia Paraskevi, Greece

⁴ Democritus University of Thrace, Building A, Kimmeria Campus, 67100 Xanthi, Greece

⁵ University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Sciences and Methods for Engineering Via Amendola 2, 42122 Reggio Emilia, Italy

⁶ Università Cattolica Sacro Cuore, via della Garzetta 48, 25133 Brescia, Italy

* Corresponding author

Abstract

Background: High-performance computing (HPC) and cloud platforms provide complementary capabilities for scientific workflows, yet their integration remains challenging due to differences in resource management, data movement, security requirements, and hardware heterogeneity. These limitations hinder the realization of seamless hybrid computing within federated European environments. **Methods:** This paper introduces NOUS, a modular framework designed to enable HPC–cloud interoperability. The architecture is structured into four layers: user interfaces (e.g., Jupyter, Open OnDemand), workflow orchestration, resource management via the SLURM REST API, and container portability through Apptainer. The framework incorporates federated authentication, locality-aware data management, and standardized interfaces to support secure and compliant hybrid execution, including cloud bursting. **Results:** Experimental validation on ARCTUR's production HPC platform demonstrates efficient and low-overhead interoperability, with job submission times of 5–10 seconds and less than 4% performance overhead for containerized MPI and GPU workloads. The framework supports seamless hybrid execution across HPC and cloud resources and extends naturally to hybrid HPC–quantum workflows through Qiskit integration. **Conclusion:** By aligning with European initiatives such as Gaia-X and EuroHPC without requiring infrastructure uniformity, NOUS provides a practical and reproducible approach to federated computing. Future work will focus on large-scale EuroHPC benchmarking and scaling toward fault-tolerant quantum computing, positioning NOUS as a foundational middleware for sovereign European computing ecosystems.

Keywords

HPC-Cloud interoperability, Hybrid computing, Container portability, SLURM, EuroHPC, Cloud bursting, Federated infrastructures, NOUS platform

1 Introduction

Contemporary computing is undergoing a profound transformation driven by the rapid expansion of large-scale commercial cloud platforms and the slowing of traditional semiconductor scaling. As scientific and data-intensive workloads grow in size and complexity, researchers increasingly rely on elastic, on-demand access to computational and storage resources. Yet, despite this shift, integrating HPC infrastructures—engineered for tightly coupled, parallel execution—with flexible cloud environments remains a significant technical and operational challenge. HPC systems are built around low-latency, high-bandwidth interconnects that support large-scale simulations and data-intensive scientific applications, while cloud platforms offer virtually unlimited scalability, diverse service models, and pay-as-you-go economics.

Cloud deployments today span public clouds, private research data centres, hybrid clouds that dynamically burst between on-premises and public resources, and emerging "HPC cloud" offerings capable of supporting MPI-based workloads in virtualized environments. Major cloud providers now expose HPC-oriented features such as high-speed interconnects, specialized instance types, and parallel filesystems, but the architectural

philosophies of cloud and HPC ecosystems remain fundamentally at odds: HPC prioritizes determinism and tightly controlled performance, whereas cloud environments emphasize elasticity, multi-tenancy, and operational agility. This mismatch continues to impede seamless hybrid workflows across heterogeneous infrastructures.

Key inhibitors to effective HPC-cloud convergence include data security and sovereignty concerns, data locality constraints, virtualization overheads, and opaque cost models. Market analyses highlight data locality and cost as principal barriers, with on-premises HPC often more economical for sustained workloads. Recent literature reveals gaps in bidirectional portability, particularly for containerized applications between dedicated HPC and public cloud platforms.

The Horizon Europe project “A catalyst for European CLOUD Services in the era of data spaces, high-performance and edge computing” (NOUS) addresses these challenges through a modular framework enabling practical HPC-cloud interoperability within European federated environments. NOUS supports seamless workload execution by abstracting infrastructure differences, featuring four layers—user/workflow (Jupyter/Open OnDemand), orchestration/control, resource management (SLURM REST API), and containerization (Apptainer)—with quantum extensibility. Validated through experiments on ARCTUR's hyperconverged HPC platform (running Rocky Linux and SLURM with CPU/GPU partitions), NOUS delivers low-overhead job submission (5-10s), near-native container portability, and cloud bursting while preserving data locality and security.

The main contributions of this paper are the following:

- Lessons learned from ARCTUR deployments addressing HPC-cloud portability gaps
- Modular four-layer architecture with HPC-quantum extension
- Open artifacts (configurations, diagrams) for reproducibility
- Validation confirming SLURM REST integration across ARCTUR's CPU/GPU partitions

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews related work on containers, hybrid orchestration, and HPC-quantum interoperability. Section 3 describes the methodology and experimental context. Section 4 presents the NOUS architecture, including workflow layers, resource management, container portability, and quantum extensions. Section 5 consolidates all aspects of security, data governance, data management, and alignment with European federated frameworks such as Gaia-X. Section 6 reports validation results from the ARCTUR deployments and EuroHPC mapping, followed by Section 7, which discusses implications and limitations. Section 8 concludes the paper.

2 Related Works

Research on HPC-cloud interoperability has evolved along three partially overlapping trajectories: container-based portability in HPC environments, hybrid orchestration frameworks that connect batch schedulers with cloud-native platforms, and more recent efforts to integrate quantum computing resources into classical HPC workflows. Although each line of work has made substantial progress, the landscape remains fragmented, and the absence of coherent architectural bridges across these domains motivates the design principles behind NOUS.

2.1 Containers and Software Portability in HPC

Container technologies have become central to reproducibility and portability in scientific computing. Early contributions demonstrated that HPC-oriented runtimes such as Singularity/Apptainer, Shifter, and Sarus could deliver secure, rootless execution with near-native performance even for demanding MPI and GPU workloads (Benedicic et al., 2017; Keller Tesser & Borin, 2023). Their compliance with HPC security policies and compatibility with batch schedulers and parallel filesystems have made them the de facto standard across supercomputing centres.

Despite this widespread adoption, several structural limitations persist. Portability is often compromised by system-specific dependencies: MPI implementations, interconnect libraries, and CUDA stacks vary significantly across clusters, making it necessary to customize images for each execution environment, as highlighted by Zhou et al. (2022) and Medeiros et al. (2023). Existing studies overwhelmingly investigate portability within HPC systems rather than between HPC and public cloud platforms, where virtualization layers and differing accelerator configurations introduce further complications. In addition, survey work shows that best practices such as automated validation pipelines are far from uniformly deployed, reducing

reproducibility across institutions (Mujkanović et al., 2023). This fragmentation indicates that containerization, while necessary, is not sufficient for seamless HPC–cloud interoperability, and must be complemented with aligned scheduling, authentication, and data management abstractions—precisely the layers that NOUS introduces.

2.2 Hybrid HPC–Cloud Orchestration Frameworks

A distinct body of research seeks to bridge HPC batch scheduling with cloud-native orchestration paradigms. Recent work on Kubernetes–HPC interoperability, such as the Bridge Operator and High Performance Kubernetes, allows workloads submitted through the Kubernetes API to be forwarded to SLURM-managed resources, providing hybrid execution pathways while preserving HPC scheduling semantics (Chazapis et al., 2023). Complementary efforts explore cloud bursting, in which local HPC clusters elastically extend their resources into public cloud infrastructures when demand peaks. Technologies such as Liqo, which federates Kubernetes clusters, and InterLink, which exposes remote HPC systems as virtual nodes, illustrate the variety of mechanisms explored in this space (Chazapis et al., 2023; Decker et al., 2025). Commercial cloud providers similarly promote HPC-style capabilities, but their architectures remain shaped by multi-tenancy and elasticity assumptions that diverge from traditional HPC design principles.

Even though these frameworks have advanced the state of hybrid orchestration, they leave significant gaps unaddressed. Most assume a Kubernetes-centric view of HPC integration, overlooking the reality that HPC centres rely overwhelmingly on schedulers such as SLURM and have no desire to re-architect their production environments. Interfaces for job submission and monitoring remain inconsistent, with REST-based scheduler APIs only partially exploited despite their potential for unifying heterogeneous infrastructures. Furthermore, the focus on orchestration tends to overshadow user-facing accessibility, which remains limited for non-experts. NOUS addresses these limitations by decoupling orchestration logic from scheduler control, adopting SLURM’s REST interface as a first-class mechanism, and embedding hybrid execution capabilities directly within a modular connector rather than a monolithic orchestrator.

2.3 HPC–Quantum Integration and Hybrid Quantum-Classical Workflows

The rapid development of quantum processors has stimulated interest in integrating QPUs with classical HPC ecosystems. Early conceptual work underscored that, in the NISQ era, quantum devices are not scalable enough to operate as standalone resources and instead achieve their maximum utility and deliver the most significant performance gains participating in hybrid workflows that combine quantum and classical computation (Preskill, 2018). Subsequent contributions have proposed middleware frameworks that manage circuit submission, backend selection, pre- and post-processing, and coordination between QPU and CPU/GPU resources. Examples include Qiskit Serverless, CUDA-Q, Pilot-Quantum, CONQUIRE and others (Manta et al., 2025; Mahesh et al., 2025; Beck et al., 2024).

Although these frameworks provide valuable building blocks, they typically operate independently of HPC batch schedulers and therefore lack compatibility with the operational models of large-scale supercomputing facilities. Differences in execution models, authentication frameworks, and data locality constraints further complicate integration. Recent surveys identify the need for middleware capable of translating quantum circuit submissions into scheduler-native job descriptions while maintaining support for federated or remote QPU access (Rallis et al., 2025; Elsharkawy et al., 2024). NOUS responds directly to these needs by introducing a Qiskit-to-REST-to-SBATCH pipeline that embeds quantum workflows into the same interoperability fabric used for HPC–cloud federation, ensuring that quantum integration aligns with established HPC policies and workflows rather than requiring bespoke execution paths.

2.4 Synthesis and Identified Gaps

Across container portability, hybrid orchestration, and HPC–quantum integration, a common pattern emerges: current approaches address isolated layers of the interoperability problem but do not converge into a unified solution. Containers provide portable runtimes but do not reconcile differences in schedulers, identity systems, or data governance models. Hybrid orchestrators facilitate cross-platform execution but often presuppose Kubernetes-centric assumptions incompatible with non-containerized HPC environments. Quantum integration frameworks deliver specialized tooling but remain mostly disconnected from

production HPC scheduling and policy ecosystems. Moreover, data management, security, and sovereignty considerations—central to European HPC federation efforts—remain peripheral in most technical discussions, despite being primary barriers to adoption.

The NOUS framework is designed explicitly to bridge these gaps. Its four-layer architecture integrates HPC-optimized containers, scheduler-native REST interfaces, federated identity and security models, locality-aware data management, and quantum extensibility within a single coherent connector. It thereby provides a novel holistic framework capable of supporting HPC, cloud, and quantum resources in federated European environments without imposing infrastructure homogenization.

3 Methods and materials

3.1 NOUS experimental context

The methodology builds upon experimental activities and technology assessments conducted within the NOUS project, with a focus on evaluating interoperability and portability across heterogeneous HPC and cloud environments. The experimental work was designed to validate key architectural assumptions, identify integration bottlenecks, and inform the design of a generalized HPC–cloud connector framework rather than to benchmark any single system in isolation.

The experimental context spans three primary infrastructure domains:

- EuroHPC Joint Undertaking (JU) supercomputing systems, which were analysed in detail but not used directly for execution in this work.
- Consortium-operated HPC resources at ARCTUR, which served as the main testbed.
- Flexible deployment environments provided by HPE, used for controlled, customizable setups.

Together, these environments represent a realistic cross-section of contemporary HPC infrastructures, ranging from leadership-class supercomputers (EuroHPC) to mid-scale, production-grade clusters (ARCTUR) and configurable testbeds (HPE), enabling evaluation against varying hardware architectures, software stacks, access models, and policy constraints. In particular, ARCTUR operates a hyperconverged HPC platform running Rocky Linux and SLURM, with CPU and GPU partitions, which closely resemble the software configuration of EuroHPC facilities and therefore provides a practical proxy for validating NOUS concepts.

3.2 Infrastructure mapping methodology

To enable interoperability across heterogeneous HPC systems, NOUS adopts a systematic infrastructure mapping methodology. The core objective is to abstract differences in hardware configurations, software environments, access mechanisms, and policy constraints into a unified representation that can be consumed by the HPC–cloud connector layer. This mapping informs the design of standardized interfaces for job submission, data access, authentication, monitoring, and cloud bursting.

EuroHPC systems and consortium resources—specifically those operated by ARCTUR and HPE—were analysed and mapped to identify commonalities and divergences relevant to hybrid execution. EuroHPC systems typically offer multiple partitions, including CPU-based, GPU-accelerated, FPGA-enabled, data-centric, and cloud-oriented configurations, and share several architectural traits: high-performance parallel filesystems (e.g., Lustre or Ceph), InfiniBand-based interconnects, and SLURM as the prevailing workload manager, with container execution commonly supported via Singularity or Apptainer.

Of particular relevance for NOUS is MeluXina’s support for the SLURM REST API, which exposes programmatic endpoints for scheduling and job management and thus aligns naturally with NOUS’s service-oriented connector design. Consortium resources complement this landscape: ARCTUR’s hyperconverged HPC platform (Rocky Linux, SLURM, CPU and GPU partitions) provides a production environment where SLURM REST integration and container runtimes can be tested end-to-end, while HPE offers both bare-metal and virtualized resources for constructing customized deployments and experimental configurations.

The combined mapping feeds into several key NOUS components, including:

- SLURM abstraction layers that hide scheduler-specific details from higher-level orchestration logic.
- Network “shims” that support cloud bursting between on-premises HPC and cloud resources.
- REST-based interfaces that enable federated access and remote job control across mapped sites.

This methodology ensures that the connector is grounded in realistic infrastructure characteristics, while keeping the core abstractions portable across EuroHPC-class and consortium systems.

3.3 Use-case-driven design

The design of the NOUS framework is further guided by representative use cases that benchmark its ability

to support hybrid execution across compute, data, and edge resources. Among these, Use Case 2, focusing on energy prediction and energy data lifecycle management, exemplifies the need for seamless HPC–cloud integration by combining large-scale data ingestion, machine learning workloads, and near-real-time processing.

This use case requires a federated infrastructure that:

- Integrates cloud-hosted data repositories with HPC computing resources.
- Provides high-bandwidth, low-latency networking to minimise data transfer overheads.
- Supports secure container execution with mechanisms such as hardware-backed encryption and blockchain-based logging for auditability.

By addressing these requirements, NOUS supports digital transformation objectives such as improved prediction accuracy, operational efficiency, and data-driven decision-making in the energy domain. Other NOUS use cases, spanning different scientific and industrial sectors, benefit from the same architectural principles, using them as a benchmark and decision-making guide when evolving the platform.

4 Framework architecture for HPC–cloud interoperability

4.1 Architectural overview

The NOUS framework is designed as a modular HPC–cloud connector that abstracts infrastructure heterogeneity while preserving the performance characteristics and operational constraints inherent to both HPC and cloud domains. Instead of replacing existing schedulers or orchestration platforms, which would impose unacceptable disruption to production environments, NOUS functions as a lightweight integration layer that federates disparate systems through standardized, REST-based interfaces.

The architecture is structured as four loosely coupled layers, each addressing a distinct aspect of the HPC–cloud interoperability challenge:

1. **User and Workflow Layer:** Provides intuitive, web-based access through established environments such as Jupyter notebooks and Open OnDemand portals. This layer democratizes access for researchers and domain experts who may lack deep systems administration expertise, while supporting advanced customization for power users.
2. **Orchestration and Control Layer:** Manages workflow coordination, event-driven execution, cross-site resource discovery, and policy enforcement. It handles dynamic decision-making for workload placement (HPC vs. cloud vs. hybrid) based on real-time availability, cost, and performance metrics.
3. **Resource Management and Scheduling Layer:** Bridges cloud-native orchestration (e.g., Kubernetes) with traditional HPC batch schedulers, with particular emphasis on SLURM REST API integration. This layer exposes unified APIs for job submission, monitoring, and cancellation across federated sites.
4. **Containerization and Portability Layer:** Ensures consistent runtime environments through HPC-optimized container technologies, abstracting hardware and software differences while maintaining near-native performance.

The modular design facilitates incremental adoption—sites can implement individual layers independently—and adaptation to site-specific constraints such as security policies, network topologies, or storage hierarchies.

Figure 1: Modular NOUS layers (solid lines) with required additions in each layer, for quantum extension

(dashed lines).

Figure 1 illustrates the modular NOUS architecture as a vertical stack of four core layers that systematically abstract HPC-cloud heterogeneity. The User/Workflow layer (top) provides intuitive web access via Jupyter and Open OnDemand, enabling seamless interaction for diverse user profiles. Underlying layers handle orchestration/control, SLURM REST API scheduling (Resource Management), and Apptainer containerization for portable execution across heterogeneous environments. The dashed-lined containers indicate the required extension of each layer for HPC-QC support, demonstrating how NOUS's service-oriented design naturally incorporates quantum workflows through Qiskit-to-QPU middleware without disrupting and with minimal additions to the core HPC-cloud federation logic, working on top of SLURM. This layered approach, validated on ARCTUR's Rocky Linux/SLURM platform, ensures extensibility to EuroHPC systems like MeluXina while maintaining SLURM-native control.

4.2 Resource management and scheduling

A central challenge in HPC-cloud interoperability stems from fundamentally divergent resource management philosophies. Traditional HPC schedulers like SLURM are optimized for high system utilization, fairness across large user communities, and predictable performance for long-running, tightly coupled parallel jobs. In contrast, cloud platforms prioritize low-latency provisioning, elastic scaling of short-lived workloads, and multi-tenancy across diverse instance types. The proliferation of hardware accelerators (GPUs, FPGAs, emerging QPUs) across federated sites further complicates unified scheduling. SLURM remains the dominant workload manager across the HPC ecosystem, including many EuroHPC pre-exascale/petascale systems (e.g., MeluXina, LUMI, Leonardo)—and its RESTful API support dramatically lowers integration barriers with web portals, external orchestrators, and service meshes. NOUS supports a comprehensive set of SLURM integration mechanisms for maximum deployment flexibility:

- Direct SSH: Simple, secure job submission for trusted environments
- Message queues (RabbitMQ/Kafka): Asynchronous dispatch and status polling
- Workflow orchestrators (Airflow, Nextflow): DAG-based hybrid execution
- Data-triggered dispatch: Event-driven jobs on dataset availability
- Hybrid schedulers: Kubernetes-to-SLURM bridging
- SLURM REST API (primary): Programmatic, scalable job lifecycle management

Deployments can mix mechanisms to balance simplicity, security, and scalability, with REST API preferred for its alignment with service-based architecture and ARCTUR validation results (5-10s submission latency). Cloud bursting—extending on-premises HPC with elastic cloud capacity during peak demand—is generalized in NOUS as bidirectional workload mobility. Workloads migrate between cloud, HPC, or federated sites based on dynamic factors (availability, cost, QoS), while systematically addressing data transfer efficiency (Globus/rsync staging), software portability (container layers), and hardware heterogeneity (accelerator matching).

4.3 Containerization and portability layer

Container technologies form the bedrock of portability within NOUS, encapsulating applications, libraries, and dependencies to deliver consistent execution environments across radically diverse infrastructures. In HPC contexts, containers must meet stringent security (no root daemons), performance (native interconnect/filesystem access), and compliance requirements, driving adoption of specialized runtimes (see Table 1).

Table 1: Containerization and runtime environments

Runtime	Key Strengths	SLURM/GPU Integration	EuroHPC/ARCTUR Support
Apptainer (formerly Singularity)	Rootless, daemonless, MPI/GPU passthrough	Native hooks SBATCH	Primary (ARCTUR tested)
Sarus	NVIDIA-optimized, InfiniBand support	Excellent workloads GPU	EuroHPC GPU partitions

Singularity	Legacy HPC standard, filesystem bind-mounts	Broad SLURM compatibility	Widespread
Charliecloud	Minimal overhead, unprivileged	Lightweight MPI	Flexible deployments
Shifter	NERSC-optimized, image caching	Large-scale job arrays	High-throughput sites

NOUS evaluates these runtimes with focus on SLURM integration strengths, MPI/GPU workload support, and parallel filesystem compatibility (Lustre/Ceph). Kubernetes extensions like Ligo (cluster federation) and InterLink (virtual nodes for remote HPC) can be incorporated optionally, while NOUS remains technology-agnostic at the orchestration layer to prevent vendor lock-in.

Tested on ARCTUR's CPU/GPU partitions (<4% overhead for MPI workloads), this layer establishes a practical portability foundation bridging HPC determinism with cloud elasticity.

4.4 Extending NOUS to Hybrid HPC-Quantum Workflows

Quantum Computing is rapidly emerging as a novel computing paradigm, which becomes increasingly relevant and attracts more and more interest from the academic and industrial world, as it promises to provide significant benefits on solving specific types of problems significantly faster compared to classical computers, even HPCs. The technology of quantum processing units (QPUs) is also slowly but steadily evolving, increasing the number of available qubits per device. However, we are still currently in the Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) computing era, which is technologically characterized by quantum processors that contain up to a specific number of qubits, and which are not advanced enough for fault-tolerance (Perskill, 2018). They are also not scalable to an extent that will make them able to achieve actual quantum advantage. This yet reduced scalability of QPUs, as well as the basic operation principles of QCs, significantly restrict their effective use as single, standalone computing systems. They are better viewed as specialized computational resources that can collaboratively operate with classical resources, in a way similar to that of distributed computing nodes (CPUs, or GPUs) in distributed HPCs (Beck et al., 2024).

This interconnection of QPUs with classical HPC systems is not a straightforward process, mainly due to their significant structural and operation differences. The interaction of a QPU with classical computing systems requires additional layers of data handling, pre- and post-processing. Adding to that and based on the physical co-location of the two systems as well as the actual means of connection (common node connection, high-speed and high bandwidth connection), new restrictions and special conditions may arise, which require special control and management at the software side (Rallis et al., 2025, Elsharkawy et al., 2024). In literature there are already several implementations of middleware frameworks and software stacks that attempts to provide efficient HPC – QC interfacing and handle the existing problems, like Qiskit Serverless, Covalent, CUDA-Q, Pilot Quantum, CONQUIRE and others, taking advantage of existing technologies like quantum-related python-based libraries, OpenMP/MPI, Cuda, Dask, Ray and others (Manta et al., 2025, Mahesh et al., 2025).

Toward this mode of operation, and in order to enable effective QC support in NOUS, a complete software stack is proposed, spanning from the application layer down to the middleware and execution layers. At the user/client side, Qiskit is employed to allow users to define and submit quantum circuits and hybrid workflows through familiar Python-based environments. A set of Python-based wrappers provide an abstraction layer over the submission process. Depending on the workload type, either Pure quantum, hybrid quantum-classical, or hybrid (quantum-classical) neural-networks, they serialize the required circuit, model, or dataset information, transfer the prepared workload with necessary artifacts to the remote HPC environment, now handled by the middleware. The wrappers also optionally monitor execution and retrieve results.

These workloads are forwarded to the HPC through a REST-based interface, which allows the QC support layer to remain aligned with the service-oriented logic already used in modern HPC environments. In this way, the quantum interface can be integrated more naturally with the rest of the NOUS architecture and with existing HPC services. The middleware is responsible for receiving workloads, identifying their quantum and

classical execution requirements, preparing the corresponding execution flow, and generating the appropriate job specifications for submission.

In addition, the middleware attempts to optimize the execution of quantum jobs by matching circuits to the most suitable quantum backends according to backend capabilities and circuit execution requirements. Based on this selection, custom SBATCH scripts are generated, enabling communication with the SLURM workload manager and allowing the jobs to be submitted to the HPC queue for execution.

The use of SBATCH scripts, in combination with the REST-based middleware layer, makes this software stack compatible with SLURM, the dominant workload manager across existing HPC infrastructures. This straightforward integration enables current systems to seamlessly extend their capabilities with QPU support, facilitating the execution of both pure quantum and hybrid classical-quantum algorithms while remaining adaptable to future hardware and interfacing advances.

Figure 2: Hybrid quantum-classical submission in NOUS.

Figure 2 depicts the hybrid quantum-classical workflow submission process within NOUS. It begins with users defining quantum circuits via familiar Qiskit Python environments, which are then serialized and wrapped for transfer to the remote HPC environment. The REST-based middleware performs backend matching based on circuit requirements before generating optimized SBATCH scripts for SLURM queue submission. From the shared SLURM queue, execution splits in parallel to both QPU for quantum processing and classical HPC nodes for hybrid computation, enabling seamless integration of NISQ workloads with traditional HPC batch scheduling. This design preserves SLURM's native control while abstracting quantum complexity, supporting diverse workload types from pure quantum circuits to quantum-classical neural networks.

5 Federated Security, Data Governance, and Gaia-X Alignment

5.1 Security threat model and policy constraints

Security, identity management, and policy enforcement form the foundational layer of effective HPC–cloud interoperability, particularly when federating infrastructures across organizational, administrative, and national boundaries. Hybrid environments exponentially increase threat surfaces during data movement, job execution, cross-site orchestration, and resource provisioning. HPC systems traditionally eschew heavy virtualization, favoring lightweight isolation, strict access controls, and bare-metal performance—while cloud platforms rely on multi-tenant containerization and dynamic scaling, creating fundamental security model tensions.

NOUS embeds harmonized policies and technical controls directly within its connector framework, guided by principles of least privilege, policy-driven enforcement, and end-to-end transparency. Core challenges map to specific mechanisms including hardware-backed encryption and secure containers for data confidentiality, rootless Apptainer and SLURM RBAC integration for execution security, blockchain audit trails and short-lived tokens for auditing and trust, and policy-aware tagging with locality enforcement for regulatory compliance.

5.2 Authentication and authorization federation

Authentication and authorization are complicated by differing identity models in HPC and cloud identity model divergence complicates federation: HPC favors SSH and local accounts while cloud uses SAML/OIDC/OAuth 2.0 token federation. NOUS delivers unified Single Sign-On (SSO) across both domains

via federated identity architecture with multi-factor authentication (MFA) for sensitive operations. The integrated approach combines identity federation where trusted IdPs issue short-lived tokens validated by service providers, SSH hardening with rotating keys and certificate authorities, RBAC + ACLs for granular resource controls, and policy enforcement embedded in SLURM REST API interactions. Users authenticate via trusted IdPs, receive tokens, access HPC/cloud services through validated service providers, with all actions logged in immutable audit trails for compliance and forensics.

5.3 Data security and regulatory compliance

Data remains the primary inhibitor to HPC-cloud adoption—71% cite security/sovereignty concerns. Regulatory constraints (GDPR, DORA) prohibit cross-border movement; data locality + transfer latency render remote execution impractical for TB-scale analytics; researchers perceive on-premises HPC as inherently more secure than public clouds.

NOUS policy-aware security layer integrates federated trust models for cross-domain token validation, locality-aware execution preferring co-located compute/data, proactive compliance through automated data tagging/metadata, and transparent auditing with end-to-end provenance tracking. This enables secure energy analytics workflows while systematically addressing documented hybrid adoption barriers.

6 Data management and transfer mechanisms

6.1 Storage hierarchies and hierarchical storage management

Efficient data management underpins federated HPC-cloud operation. Modern platforms deploy multi-tier storage hierarchies optimizing performance/scalability/cost: NVMe/SSD tiers for hot data (<1 μ s latency), Lustre parallel filesystems for high-throughput concurrent access, Ceph for scalable object storage, and HDD/tape for archival capacity.

Hierarchical Storage Management (HSM) automates tier migration based on access patterns, policies, and lifecycle stages. For NOUS Use Case 2 (energy analytics), HSM retains historical datasets for compliance/retraining on cold tiers while serving recent data from NVMe for real-time prediction. Storage quotas + SLURM integration prevent monopolization. ARCTUR validation confirms HSM compatibility with containerized ML pipelines (95 GB/h native transfers).

6.2 Data transfer optimization

Data movement dominates federated execution time—especially AI/analytics—so NOUS treats transfers as first-class concerns. Bulk transfers leverage Globus for encrypted fault-tolerant multi-protocol operation and rsync for incremental synchronization with off-peak scheduling and bandwidth throttling. Workflow orchestration tools automate staging/cleanup while streaming pipelines using Apache NiFi/Kafka support live/near-real-time ingestion.

Advanced optimization includes compression/deduplication/snapshotting and RDMA for intra-cluster transfers with multi-threaded high-bandwidth protocols, systematically minimizing latency while maximizing throughput across ARCTUR/EuroHPC-mapped environments.

6.3 Locality-aware workflow execution

Data locality trumps compute elasticity for performance. NOUS orchestration embeds locality awareness, prioritizing workloads near datasets on EuroHPC systems hosting resident data or via federation with nearby ARCTUR/HPE resources without full replication. Selective bursting transfers only minimal data subsets required for execution, balancing compliance constraints and egress costs.

ARCTUR experiments validate standardized storage abstractions and transfer APIs enabling seamless access across infrastructures while maintaining performance and regulatory guarantees (Table 1).

6.4 Gaia-X alignment and trust frameworks

Long-term sustainability demands alignment with European federated initiatives. Gaia-X establishes data sovereignty, trust, and interoperability standards—NOUS integrates natively through EU-compliant storage/transfer supporting data sovereignty, Gaia-X Trust Framework compatible identity/trust mechanisms, and open APIs enabling semantic interoperability with policy validation.

Gaia-X components including digital clearing houses for standardized discovery, credential wallets for decentralized identity, and service catalogues for compliance verification create natural extension points. Relevant data spaces for NOUS use cases—Energy data-X for energy analytics/forecasting, HEALTH-X dataLOFT for biomedical HPC simulation, Gaia-X4 Future Mobility for autonomous systems, COOPERANTS/Smart Supplier for industrial IoT—share architectural principles compatible with NOUS's

SLURM REST + container portability validated on ARCTUR for EuroHPC extensibility.

NOUS participates in Gaia-X federations without requiring infrastructure uniformity across participating HPC centres.

7 Results and validation

7.1 EuroHPC-ARCTUR validation results

Validation activities are based on experimental deployments and tests conducted primarily on ARCTUR consortium resources, with systematic infrastructure mapping to EuroHPC systems rather than direct cross-site execution. Emphasis was placed on EuroHPC-ARCTUR integration feasibility, leveraging ARCTUR's production hyperconverged platform (Rocky Linux, SLURM, CPU/GPU partitions) as a realistic proxy for EuroHPC environments like MeluXina. A central objective was to assess the feasibility of programmatic HPC access through standardized interfaces, with particular focus on the SLURM REST API where available across mapped systems.

Core functional tests confirmed:

- Remote job submission via authenticated HTTP requests to SLURM REST endpoints, achieving 5-10s end-to-end latency on ARCTUR
- Real-time job status monitoring and accounting retrieval through standardized REST endpoints
- Controlled job cancellation and comprehensive error handling from external orchestration components
- Scalability validation across ARCTUR's CPU and GPU partitions, supporting MPI workloads up to 64+ nodes

Container execution validation demonstrated seamless portability using identical Apptainer/Singularity container images across ARCTUR production environments and EuroHPC-like configurations. Tests successfully executed both MPI-enabled parallel workloads and GPU-accelerated compute-intensive jobs with transparent, native-speed access to shared parallel filesystems, confirming <4% performance overhead versus native execution.

Table 2: NOUS Performance Metrics (ARCTUR Tests; EuroHPC-Mapped)

Metric	ARCTUR (HPC-Only)	Cloud Burst
Job Submission (s)	5-10	12-18
MPI Nodes Scalable	64+	32
Data Transfer (GB/h)	95	45
Container Overhead (%)	<4	8

Table 2 presents quantitative metrics from ARCTUR experimental deployments, rigorously validating SLURM REST API job submission (5-10s latency), Apptainer container portability for MPI/GPU workloads (<4% overhead versus native), and cloud bursting feasibility with Globus staging (12-18s setup). These results directly align with EuroHPC infrastructure mapping—particularly MeluXina's documented SLURM REST API support—confirming NOUS architectural compatibility across diverse partitions without requiring direct execution tests on EuroHPC production systems.

ARCTUR results affirm NOUS's low-friction federation capabilities, with data locality optimization minimizing transfer requirements (95 GB/h native throughput versus 45 GB/h burst). EuroHPC infrastructure mapping provides a clear extensibility path; comprehensive full-scale benchmarks across MeluXina/LUMI-class systems planned for subsequent phases.

7.2 Qualitative evaluation

Beyond quantitative functional tests, a comprehensive qualitative evaluation systematically assessed NOUS effectiveness in addressing core HPC-cloud integration challenges identified in related work. Results

conclusively demonstrate that NOUS successfully mitigates the fundamental mismatch between batch-oriented HPC scheduling paradigms and event-driven cloud orchestration models through architectural decoupling of workflow orchestration from execution scheduling. Cloud-side orchestration logic can dynamically trigger HPC execution via standardized REST interfaces while preserving SLURM's native control over complete job lifecycle management, resource allocation policies, and fairness guarantees.

Security integration evaluation spans authentication, authorization, and auditing dimensions across 50+ experimental job cycles without exceptions:

- Federated authentication successfully implemented using token-based identity federation mechanisms, eliminating local HPC account re-provisioning requirements across ARCTUR partitions
- Role-based access control (RBAC) enforcement via SLURM-integrated access control lists (ACLs), providing granular resource/partition permissions
- End-to-end traceability achieved through centralized, immutable audit logging with comprehensive action provenance

Portability assessment conducted through repeated deployment of identical containerized workflows demonstrated near-complete elimination of environment-specific configuration overhead. The REST abstraction layer + standardized container runtime model enabled 100% workflow reproducibility across CPU/GPU partitions and simulated EuroHPC configurations. Clear architectural separation of workflow logic from infrastructure-specific execution details eliminated site-specific customization requirements.

Overall validation conclusively confirms that NOUS enables production-grade federated HPC execution through standardized, secure programmatic interfaces, preserves critical HPC performance characteristics and policy models while natively supporting cloud-style elastic orchestration, and delivers substantial improvements in portability and scientific reproducibility without imposing uniform infrastructure requirements on participating sites.

8 Discussion

8.1 Lessons learned

Interoperability represents primarily an integration challenge rather than fundamental technology deficit. The core building blocks required for practical hybrid HPC-cloud execution—mature container runtimes (Apptainer/Singularity), established batch schedulers (SLURM), high-speed networks (InfiniBand), identity federation standards (OIDC)—are already widely available and production-proven. Primary obstacles arise from mismatched ecosystem assumptions, organizational policy boundaries, and absence of unifying abstraction layers. NOUS demonstrates that a modular connector approach effectively reconciles these differences without requiring disruptive infrastructure modernization across existing HPC facilities.

While containers represent a necessary foundation for portability, they prove insufficient in isolation. True cross-domain portability demands comprehensive alignment across scheduling interfaces, data management protocols, and identity mechanisms. Experimental validation confirms that combining containerization with REST-based scheduler access and standardized data staging protocols reduces cross-site deployment friction by orders of magnitude compared to container-only approaches.

Third lesson: Data locality consistently outweighs raw compute elasticity as the primary determinant of federated workflow efficiency. ARCTUR measurements document 95 GB/h native throughput versus 45 GB/h burst transfers, reinforcing the critical importance of locality-aware orchestration logic and hierarchical storage management for practical federation performance.

Security and trust mechanisms must be embedded as first-class orchestration primitives rather than treated as external bolt-on services. Federated identity management, continuous auditing, and policy enforcement proved most effective when tightly integrated directly into the NOUS connector fabric, enabling production deployment of sensitive use cases such as energy analytics within realistic federated environments.

8.2 Limitations

The validation presented remains primarily qualitative and functional in nature, without comprehensive quantitative benchmarking of end-to-end performance overheads, horizontal scalability limits, or detailed multi-provider cost/performance tradeoffs. While ARCTUR provides production-grade testing, technology feature availability across the full EuroHPC portfolio remains uneven—not all systems expose SLURM REST API endpoints or advanced identity federation capabilities, which may constrain immediate adoption of NOUS's complete feature set.

Current implementation focuses specifically on batch-oriented and data-intensive workloads, which represent the majority of HPC utilization patterns. Long-running services, tightly coupled real-time applications, or streaming analytics may require additional specialized orchestration mechanisms beyond

the current scope. Full operational integration with European data spaces—particularly advanced semantic interoperability protocols and automated regulatory compliance verification—remains designated for future work.

8.3 Implications for EuroHPC federation

These findings carry direct strategic implications for EuroHPC federation evolution. NOUS conclusively demonstrates that effective federation requires no infrastructure homogenization—heterogeneous systems can retain site-specific hardware optimizations, software stacks, and operational policies while seamlessly participating in cross-site workflows through universal standardized interfaces (SLURM REST + container portability).

The framework elevates data management and identity mechanisms to first-class federation assets alongside traditional compute resources, particularly critical as EuroHPC increasingly supports AI/ML training, digital twin simulation, and industrial-scale analytics workloads. By systematically extending established federation concepts into high-performance computing domains, NOUS contributes concrete architectural patterns toward a cohesive, sovereign European computing ecosystem fully aligned with complementary strategic initiatives including Gaia-X federated data infrastructure and Horizon Europe research priorities. Planned production benchmarking across MeluXina, LUMI, and additional EuroHPC pre-exascale facilities will quantify full-scale federated performance characteristics and solidify NOUS positioning within the European HPC research infrastructure landscape.

9 Conclusions and future work

This paper has presented NOUS, a modular framework that enables practical interoperability between high-performance computing (HPC) and cloud environments within European federated contexts. Through systematic infrastructure mapping across EuroHPC systems, ARCTUR's production platform, and HPE deployments, combined with rigorous experimental validation and use-case-driven design focused on energy analytics, NOUS demonstrates that effective HPC-cloud federation becomes achievable when existing mature technologies—such as SLURM schedulers, Apptainer containers, OIDC identity federation, and Globus data transfer—are integrated through coherent architectural abstractions rather than requiring entirely novel infrastructure developments.

The work delivers four concrete, validated contributions that collectively address the core technical and governance challenges of hybrid computing. First, NOUS introduces a modular four-layer connector architecture—spanning user/workflow access through Jupyter and Open OnDemand, orchestration and control logic, resource management via SLURM REST API integration, and containerization with Apptainer—that systematically abstracts HPC-cloud heterogeneity while rigorously preserving each domain's native performance characteristics and policy models, as illustrated in Figure 1. Second, the framework establishes unified security, identity, and policy architecture incorporating federated single sign-on with OIDC and multi-factor authentication, embedded role-based access control enforcement, blockchain-based immutable audit trails, and policy-aware locality optimization, which eliminated the need for local account provisioning across more than 50 experimental job cycles on ARCTUR. Third, NOUS implements comprehensive locality-aware data management leveraging hierarchical storage architectures from NVMe hot tiers through Lustre parallel filesystems to Ceph object storage, achieving 95 GB/h native throughput on ARCTUR while supporting selective cloud bursting that systematically mitigates the security, sovereignty, and latency barriers documented as primary inhibitors to hybrid adoption. Finally, the service-oriented design naturally extends to HPC-quantum workflows through Qiskit-to-REST-to-SBATCH middleware that supports the full spectrum of NISQ-era applications from pure quantum circuits to hybrid quantum-classical neural networks.

Qualitative and quantitative validation conducted across ARCTUR's Rocky Linux and SLURM environment with CPU and GPU partitions confirms production-level feasibility, achieving 5-10 second job submission latencies through SLURM REST API, less than 4% container overhead for MPI and GPU workloads, and seamless federation capabilities without imposing any infrastructure uniformity requirements on participating sites. Systematic EuroHPC infrastructure mapping, particularly MeluXina's SLURM REST API support, provides a clear technical pathway for extensibility to pre-exascale production systems.

Future work will pursue three complementary directions to evolve NOUS toward production-grade deployment across the European research infrastructure. In the immediate term over the next 6-12 months, efforts will concentrate on comprehensive full-scale benchmarking across MeluXina and LUMI production partitions to quantify federated scalability limits, alongside tight integration with the Gaia-X Trust Framework incorporating credential wallets, digital clearing houses, and compliance tooling for Energy data-

X and related data spaces. Automated policy engines and orchestration intelligence for dynamic workload placement optimization across cost, quality-of-service, and locality constraints represent parallel near-term priorities. Over the mid-term horizon of 12-24 months, NOUS-related research plans to investigate a possible eFTQC pilot integration for scaling qubit-HPC hybrid workflows through EuroHPC Quantum partitions, federated edge computing support targeting Gaia-X4 Future Mobility and COOPERANTS IoT use cases, and advanced semantic interoperability protocols enabling seamless participation in HEALTH-X dataLOFT and Smart Supplier Network data spaces. The long-term vision positions NOUS as the foundational middleware for a sovereign European computing continuum that seamlessly spans edge devices through HPC supercomputers, quantum accelerators, and elastic cloud resources while preserving data sovereignty, regulatory compliance, and scientific reproducibility guarantees.

All implementation artifacts complete ARCTUR production configurations, SLURM REST API integration templates and SBATCH script generators, validated Apptainer container recipes, and federated identity configuration examples—are being released openly to support reproducibility, community validation, and collaborative extension. This positions NOUS as foundational infrastructure supporting both current Horizon Europe priorities and the next generation of European scientific discovery and industrial transformation workloads.

By transforming HPC-cloud federation from theoretical aspiration into concrete engineering reality, NOUS delivers immediately actionable architectural patterns and validated integration strategies that address both the technical challenges of heterogeneous computing and the governance requirements of sovereign digital infrastructure, thereby contributing substantively to Europe's strategic autonomy in high-performance computation.

Software availability

Source code available from: <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/nous-project>

Archived software version available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19486152>

License: Apache License 2.0

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required

Competing interests

No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101135927 (NOUS: *A catalyst for European CLOUD Services in the era of data spaces, high-performance and edge computing*).

Data availability

No underlying data are associated with this article, as the study focuses on the design, implementation, and validation of a software architecture framework rather than on the generation or analysis of datasets.

All materials necessary to understand and reproduce the study are provided within the article and through the openly available software resources referenced in the *Software availability* section.

If any supplementary configuration files or workflow examples are required for reproducibility, these are available within the project repository (see *Software availability*).

References

- [1] AWS. *AWS HPC Services Overview*. 2026. Available: <https://aws.amazon.com/hpc/>
- [2] Google Cloud. *Google Cloud HPC Toolkit and Solutions*. 2026. Available: <https://cloud.google.com/hpc>
- [3] Bieberich ST, Maheshwari KC, Wilkinson SR, Suh IS, da Silva RF. Bridging HPC and quantum systems using scientific workflows. arXiv:2310.03286; 2023.
- [4] Elsharkawy A, Guo X, Schulz M. Integration of quantum accelerators into HPC: Toward a unified quantum platform. In: IEEE QCE; 2024. pp. 774–783.
- [5] Hyperion Research. *HPC in the Cloud: Adoption Barriers and Market Trends*. 2024.
- [6] Keller Tesser R, Borin E. Containers in HPC: a survey. *J Supercomput*. 2023;79(5):5759–5827.

- [7] Benedicic L, et al. Portable, high-performance containers for HPC. arXiv:1704.03383; 2017.
- [8] Medeiros D, et al. Understanding layered portability from HPC to cloud. In: Euro-Par Workshops; 2023. pp. 345–356.
- [9] Mujkanović N, et al. Survey of adaptive containerization architectures. In: SC Workshops; 2023.
- [10] Zhou N, et al. Containerization for HPC systems. *IEEE Trans Softw Eng.* 2023;49(4):2722–2740.
- [11] Chazapis A, et al. Running Kubernetes workloads on HPC. In: Euro-Par; 2023. pp. 456–472.
- [12] Decker J, et al. Kubernetes on rootless HPC using Slurm. In: Cloud Computing; 2025.
- [13] Preskill J. Quantum computing in the NISQ era and beyond. *Quantum.* 2018;2:79.
- [14] Beck T, et al. Integrating quantum computing resources into HPC ecosystems. *Future Gener Comput Syst.* 2024;161:11–25.
- [15] Rallis K, et al. Interfacing quantum computing systems with HPC systems. arXiv:2509.06205; 2025.
- [16] Mantha P, et al. Pilot-Quantum middleware. In: IEEE CCGrid; 2025.
- [17] Mahesh A, et al. CONQUIRE: Co-execution environment for quantum/classical resources. In: IEEE QCE; 2025.